

A replicable framework for institutional change

Impact & Transferability

- ✓ Validated in **7 European universities**.
- ✓ Ready for adoption by other **universities across Europe, University alliances, national agencies and EU programmes**.
- ✓ Promotes **inclusive, open and sustainable innovation**.

CATALISI provides a replicable and scalable roadmap for universities to lead sustainable institutional transformation through co-creation, learning, and innovation.

www.catalisi.eu

The CATALISI framework follows a cyclical pathway guiding HEIs from identifying transformation needs to achieving sustainable institutional change. Living Labs and the co-created Transformational Pathway act as transversal mechanisms supporting all stages.

CATALISI Replicable Framework of Acceleration Services

A methodological pathway for institutional transformation in Higher Education Institutions.

CATALISI | Catalysation of institutional transformations of Higher Education Institutions through the adoption of acceleration services. Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement n. 101094917. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Vision

The CATALISI framework offers a structured, adaptable and evidence-based approach that empowers Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to lead systemic change in Research & Innovation (R&I).

Purpose

Support universities in embedding transformation into their strategy, governance and operations through a structured process and targeted acceleration services. In particular, it helps to:

- Embed institutional transformation strategically.
- Align with European Research Area (ERA) and European Education Area (EEA).
- Promote participatory and evidence-based decision-making.
- Foster peer learning and collaboration across HEIs.

Not a one-size-fits-all model, but a modular and flexible approach tailored to each institution.

Why it matters

Promotes systemic and sustainable change in R&I.

Ensures alignment with EU policy priorities (ERA & EEA).

Encourages participatory governance and cross-institutional collaboration.

Tested in 7 European HEIs, proving its scalability and flexibility.

The 5-Step Transformation Process

1. Define Strategic Intervention Areas

Purpose: identify the areas within the university that require targeted transformation to better align institutional strategies with ERA and EEA priorities.

2. Co-create and design the Transformational Pathway on the selected area of change

Purpose: Activate an Acting Living Lab (a participatory space) to co-design a Transformational Pathway and Action Plan with key stakeholders, guided by a Theory of Change and SMART KPIs.

3. 1st Implementation cycle and formative evaluation

Purpose: Launch the 1st implementation cycle with the support of modular acceleration services and use formative evaluation to align, monitor, and refine actions toward institutional goals.

4. 2nd Implementation cycle & institutional anchoring

Purpose: Launch the 2nd implementation cycle, embed the updated Action Plan and Transformational Pathway into governance and policies, ensuring that transformation becomes part of long-term institutional structures.

5. Consolidation, sustainability and transfer

Purpose: Consolidate results, build a sustainability roadmap, and leverage the CATALYST Hub and Communities of Practices to replicate and scale transformation across HEIs.

7 Innovation Acceleration Services

Modular, replicable, and scalable innovative tools designed to accelerate change and adaptable to diverse contexts.

Living Lab

Leverage a co-creation methodology for university innovation development

Counselling

Empower HEIs through mentoring and coaching

Transformational Pathway

Enhance HEIs' ability to respond to societal challenges effectively

Predictive Study on Skills Anticipation

Support in re-thinking investments in education and training

Catalyst Hub

Digital platform designed to facilitate cooperation

Community of Practice

Support in re-thinking investments in education and training

Capacity Building and Outreach

Invest in human resources to foster economic growth, social development, and innovation